

LINGUISTIC CORPUS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article focuses on relationship between corpus linguistics (CL) and language teaching (LT) and provide an overview of the most important pedagogical applications of corpora. While LT profits from the resources, methods, and insights provided by CL, it also provides important impulses that are taken up in corpus linguistic research. The present article will investigate what influence CL has had on LT so far, and in what ways corpora have been used to improve pedagogical practice. It will also discuss further possible effects of CL on LT .*

The process of information globalization is increasingly visible in the world community. The level of information technology development affects the state of the economy, the quality of people's lives, national security and the role of the state in the world community. The process of informatization has also affected the education system. Currently, the main task in this area is to improve the quality of the educational process and use modern information technologies to improve the level of education. One such example is the Internet. The global network today occupies about 50% of interpersonal communication. And after all, it is the goal of education. Communicating, a person should be able to understand the information provided, effectively and clearly build his speech. Consequently, the success of interlingua communication directly depends on the level of the foreign communicative competence formed.

The application of corpora in language teaching, this includes both the use of corpus tools, i.e. the actual text collections and software packages for corpus access, and of corpus methods, i.e. the analytic techniques. In classifying pedagogical corpus applications, i.e. the use of corpus tools and methods in a language teaching and language learning context, a useful distinction (going back to Leech 1997) can be made between direct and indirect applications. This means that, 'indirectly', corpora can help with decisions about what to teach and when to teach it, but that they can also be accessed 'directly' by learners and teachers in the LT classroom, and so "assist in the teaching process" (Fligelstone 1993, 98), thus affecting how something is taught and learnt.

Large general corpora have proven to be an invaluable resource in the design of language teaching syllabi which emphasize communicative competence (cf. Hymes 1972, 1992) and which give prominence to those items that learners are most likely to encounter in real life communicative situations. In the context of computer corpus-informed English language teaching syllabi, the first and probably most groundbreaking development was the design of the Collins COBUILD English Course (CCEC; Willis/Willis 1989), an offshoot of the pioneering COBUILD project in pedagogically oriented lexicography (cf. Sinclair 1987; articles 3 and 8).

“From the very beginning of the training, situations should be developed where the student remains self-left and will have to use the language in its natural function”- as W. M. Rivers wrote - establishing and maintaining relations with other people, receiving and transmitting information, expressing one’s attitude towards something, learning to do something, concealing one’s intentions, using words to break out of a difficult situation, the ability to persuade and dissuade others, and so on.

There are a significant number of works entirely based on cases (such as dictionaries and grammar) and available to teachers and students, as well as developments on the use of concordances and exercises based on work with cases that can be used in class. It is quite difficult to find the modern dictionary of a well-known publishing house, which would not have been compiled on the basis of a linguistic corpus. The body data forced scientists to take a fresh look at their ideas about the language and revise the approach to compiling grammatical and lexical handbooks, textbooks and other materials for those wishing to learn a foreign language. Thus, the contribution of corpus linguistics to the description of the language, as well as to the methodology of teaching foreign languages, is difficult to challenge. Corpus linguistics introduces innovative changes in scientific methods and technologies and, possibly, anticipates the emergence of even more fundamental changes that will confront traditional ideas about education, the role of the teacher, and the cultural context of providing educational services. The use of case data as an empirical component of lecture courses, student assignments and independent projects becomes the everyday practice in leading universities in the world. It turns out that the corpus approach is optimal for visual representation of such aspects of the language as historical, geographical and social variation and changes in the linguistic system, while giving a viable opportunity to master the basic principles of hull methods of linguistic analysis. Significant assistance in this area can be provided by the use of the methods of case linguistics: automated extraction of information, training on the basis of data, text searches in large-scale buildings using natural language processing methods.

Corpus linguistics uses mono- and multilingual corpus of texts, which are often annotated with linguistically significant information, for example, parts of speech, lemmas, morphological features, syntactic structure. semantic interpretation.

The linguistic corpus has long been used for educational purposes, for example, the linguists Freese, Trever and Bongers used the linguistic corps in studies on pedagogy and the method of teaching foreign languages.

Corpus linguistics is a section of computer linguistics that deals with the development of linguistic buildings, the principles of their construction and functioning, the study of relations arising at the level of "corpus of texts - its separate text", and "Development of technologies for managing technological processes. In order for the corpus to meet the requirements of authenticity, it is necessary that it collects texts selected from real communicative situations, unlike artificially created by linguists themselves for the achievement of certain research objectives or collected as a result of the experiment in artificially created conditions, only reminding the real conditions of communication.

The national building is created by linguists (specialists in so-called corpus linguistics, a rapidly developing modern field of linguistics) for scientific research and language training. Most major languages of the world already have their own national corpus, differing in the completeness and level of scientific processing of texts. The British National Corps (BNC) is an established example. Many other modern buildings are oriented towards it. The National Corpus has two important features:

Firstly, it is characterized by a representative, or balanced composition of texts. This means that the corpus contains as much as possible all types of written and spoken texts presented in the given language (artistic genres, journalistic, educational, scientific, business, colloquial, dialectal, etc.) and that all the above texts are included in the body if possible in proportion to their share in the language of the relevant period. It should be borne in mind that good representativeness is achieved only with a significant body volume (tens and hundreds of millions of usage). Secondly, the corpus contains special additional information on the properties of the texts included in it (so-called markup, or annotation). Layout is the main characteristic of the case. It distinguishes the corpus from simple collections (or "libraries") of texts that are abundantly presented on the Internet. For the compilers of the National Corpus, factors such as the fascination or usefulness of the book, its high artistic or scientific merits are important, but not paramount. The national building, unlike the electronic library, is not a collection of "interesting" or "useful" texts for learning the language. And such may be, along with classical works of fiction, the novel of a minor writer, and the recording of an ordinary telephone conversation, and a typical lease agreement, etc.

The National Corpus is designed to provide scientific research on the vocabulary and grammar of the language, as well as the subtle but continuous processes of linguistic changes occurring in the language over relatively short periods - from one to two centuries. Another function of the corpus is to provide all kinds of references related to the specified areas (vocabulary, grammar, accentology, history of the language). Students should act not only as active participants in the discourse, but also as its observers, researchers, so studying typical ways of organizing a language and using it in a variety of styles genres affects the degree of authenticity when using the language by students in real communication or in written speech. In other words, students use the corpus to find information to solve a particular communicative task, analyze search results, and so on. The goal of the teachers is to help students "see the patterns in the target language and formulate generalizations, rules" of using the language, and students in turn should behave in the learning process as "language detectives", independently exploring a particular discourse, the contexts of using words, to the conclusions and try to formulate the rules of grammar using the deductive method.

In conclusion, the use of linguistic corpus in teaching a foreign language makes it possible to evaluate the use of various word-formations and word-combinations directly by native speakers, i.e. to study "living language". Moreover, the linguistic corpus makes it possible to track changes and transformations in the language, as it is constantly updated; allows the learners to draw their own conclusions. For teachers, the linguistic corpus is a new opportunity in the methodology of teaching foreign languages.

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